

Table 6. Grid 4. Links to other by STEM subject, channel and links, description and gender

Channel and links	Description	Gender
<i>Ciencia XL</i>	Quantum physics, CERN matters, Cosmos, Physics experiemnts and featured channels.	Man
Eight links, one of woman, 6 of men and one of man/woman. Links, among others, to	72. <i>ScenioTV</i> (long videos, collective recordings. Documentary character, strong use of formats (image, video, drawings, collective video-conferences) and games in ScenioCraft. Long videos (most over an hour and a half)	Man and woman
	73. <i>Antroporama</i> , by Patri Tezanos. Information about the human being, the science of love and attraction, phenomena, awareness, tests and experiments.	Woman
<i>Huele a Química</i> ,	Scientific teaching, Chemistry	Man
12 channels linked, 3 of women	<i>Viajando por planetas</i> , by Laura M. Parro, pre-doctoral student in Planetary Science.	Woman
Links, among others, to	<i>Date un Vlog</i> – A new way of understanding education. Speculative physics, cosmology, astronomy, quantum physics and relativity	Man
<i>Quantum Fracture</i> links to <i>TheQuantumFracture</i> that links to 12, 2 woman/man, 1 woman, 9 men	Physics and dissemination of time, gravity, electricity	Man
<i>TheQuantumFracture</i> among others, links to	74. <i>TheQuantumFracture</i> - Einstein, Earth, Universe (English)	Woman
	75. <i>Minuto de Ciencia</i> , on Physics (English)	Man
	76. <i>MinuteEarth</i> (in English): Earth, space, animals, geology, ecology, links to “Minute of” in French, Arabic. Very educational with cartoons (less than 30 seconds)	Woman and man
	77. <i>Veritasium</i> (in English): Mathematics, physics, dissemination, funny mistakes in science. Includes songs (he sings)	Man
	78. <i>CGP Grey</i> (English, subtitled): Exploration, Minecraft type games, about society and nature. Fair amount of drawings.	Man
<i>FISICALIMITE</i> , links to 7 channels: one woman, 6 men.	Physics	Man
Links, among others, to	80. <i>Kurzgesagt – In a Nutshell</i> (English): Man's voice-over and animation	Man
	81. <i>MinutoDeFísica</i> (English): Man's voice-over and animation	Man
<i>Sábados culturetas</i> , links to 5 men	Experiments, nature with a touch of humour	Woman
<i>CienciadeSofa</i> links to 3, one woman (already mentioned), 2 men	Physics, periodical table, meteorites, chemistry	Man